

AN INTERPRETATIVE PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF GRADUATING COLLEGE STUDENTS ON CAREER UNCERTAINTIES

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ABSTRACT

This study explored graduating college students within different programs with career uncertainty and how its emergence transpires in their everyday circumstances. Eight (8) graduating college students, ages 20-23 from universities and colleges in the National Capital Region (NCR) were interviewed through a semi-structured guide formulated by the researchers, and gathered data were analyzed by utilizing Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Findings revealed that career uncertainty takes shape into experiences through six themes: (a) reasons of career uncertainty; (b) challenges in experiencing career uncertainty; (c) manifestations of career uncertainty; (d) managing career uncertainty: coping efficacy; (e) persevering amidst career uncertainty; and (f) making sense with uncertainty. This study exclusively focuses on graduating college students residing in the National Capital Region (NCR) within a wide range of programs. Career Decision-making Difficulties Questionnaire (CDDQ) is also involved in the study as a qualifier to measure the participants' level of career uncertainty. With this study's objective to highlight the phenomenon in the Filipino context, Filipino cultural values such as *bahala na*, *kapwa*, and *pakikipagkapwa* surfaced upon the identified data analysis. Despite these experiences, participants yield their own way of responding to the challenges they encounter, which makes career uncertainty a phenomenon. Graduating college students are the next generation to enter the workforce. Adapting contemporary studies on their personal experiences in various career prospects guides effective career development programs and interventions by focusing on sustainable work performance while also taking into account the well-being of workers.

Keywords: *Career Uncertainty, Uncertainty, Graduating, College Students, Coping Efficacy, Challenges, Manifestation, Management Strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

Career uncertainty, which is considered to have a negative impact on individuals, has garnered significant attention. Levels of uncertainty are consistently manifested in their career choices as the government introduces the K–12 curriculum (Barayuga & Ramirez, 2021). In the presence of career uncertainty, graduates of baccalaureate programs in college hold their position, as their situation is still unfortunate and hopeless, yet they continue to respond to the contrasting challenges they're experiencing (Ortiga, 2018). Experiences of career uncertainty turn their decision-making capability into career indecision (Elyadi, 2006, as cited by Botha & Mostert, 2013).

Manapsal (2018) reveals the ranking of undecidability factors of senior high school students primarily financial problems, followed by decision making immaturity, limitation of choices in school, pressure from peers, Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the institutions are not yet credited, other left unanswered reasons, and lastly, problems in health. In the study of career decision-making difficulties conducted at Cebu Doctors' University, it shows that the commonly indecisive were the lack of readiness and in career making difficulties, dysfunctional beliefs are present. Due to internal and external conflicts, including unreliable information, problems are also experienced considering the inconsistency of information. (Chambel, Salimbata, and Licatan, 2017).

Goodson (2018) states that many college students show uncertainty when it comes to their career paths and by the time they step foot in tertiary education, this includes the initiative of selecting a college program wherein uncertainty is extended regarding their probabilities about their future career. An indication of uncertainty initially emerges in the beginning of their college journey and as they progress towards more advanced levels of education, their uncertainty continues to grow. Moreover, college students in their senior year are already in their phase of concluding their studies where graduation becomes one of the highlights of their lives. Graduating college students are still uncertain about their futures due to the many factors they encountered along the way. Graduates' career-entry concerns include the perceived inability to find an "appropriate" job in the future (Ebner, K., Soucek, R., & Selenko, 2021). According to the research of Kwok (2018), career uncertainty carries multiple directions in an individual's process of achieving goals and these often change due to the labor market's unpredictability. Even though there is a definite measure of changes and inevitable uncertainty due to the intersection of different forces such as socio-political and economic forces that made projections to the corporate world and the market of employment.

Rahmadani & Sahrani (2021), one of the final-year college students' important aspects is their future careers. This involves becoming independent and having a financial perspective regarding meeting their needs in the future. Graduating college students' main goal is to get an appropriate job that aligns to their field, where they can grow and

expand their skills. But, their concern is the higher jobless rate in 2023 that is also possibly expected, as more graduates will be participating in the stirring convention of seeking jobs/work in the Filipino community (de Vera & Corrales, 2022). In connection with this, Schaal (2015) states that job opportunities will decrease due to high uncertainty and this will ultimately lead to an escalation towards unemployment.

This study aims to investigate the lived experiences of graduating college students who are experiencing career uncertainty and identify the causes behind it. The study might be helpful to provide the basis that will benefit educational institutions, specifically school counselors, in enhancing systematic career development interventions.

Figure 1: Career Uncertainty Model (Tien et al., 2005)

This study was utilized based on Hsiu-Lan Shelly Tien, Chia-Huei Lin, and Shu-Chi Chen's Career Uncertainty Model in 2005 that focused on the experiences of the moment of uncertainty and coping efficacy regarding uncertainty through the college student's insights or point of view. It focuses more on an individual's encounter with the current presence of uncertainty and coping approaches from the uncertainty's foundation. It presents how career uncertainty across the individual's process of decision-making plays an important role; thus, uncertainty in different aspects—behavioral, emotional, and cognitive—shows negative feelings the moment they experience it.

In this study, we utilized only the specific aspects of the model to analyze the in-depth experiences of the graduating college students in the Philippines but also to identify the personal and environmental reasons that mold their career uncertainty. In relation to cultural differences, we modified components of the model to be suitable for application in the Philippine context as the groundwork analysis that produced the model is built upon the perception of Taiwanese college students. Primarily, the researchers adapted the three domains of the career uncertainty experience namely: physical, emotional, and cognitive. Moreover, modifying the use of coping efficacies as it pertains to the adjustments made to cope with the feeling of uncertainty by the college students in Taiwan, wherein it differs with the support that Filipino graduating college students obtain from their social relationships that aids them in managing and persevering through their career uncertainty.

Graduating College Students

According to the data released by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2023), unemployment within Filipinos rose to 2.31 million this January and higher compared to last month's number of 2.22 million. Thus, the Filipino unemployment rate continues to rise to 2.37 million, which is estimated at 4.8 percent. This percentage climbs from 4.3 percent in the previous months of 2023 (PSA, 2023; Manila Bulletin, 2023). Graduating college students from various universities and colleges are presumed to join the workforce in 2023, which means that the market labor must be prepared for the 1.5 million individuals as the unemployment rate continues to rise. If the government does not prioritize addressing the problem of workers' preparedness and job generation, it will face unemployment and underemployment problems (MB, 2023; GMA News, 2023).

Perna (2021) states that only a third of college students believe that once they graduate, they are able to land the job that they want. They know with uncertainty that they are entering a labor market fraught with uncertainty. Due to the recovery of the economy, the younger generations may well recover with it from their natural optimism. The study involved undergraduates still attending the university and found that many college students, in a late 20th century mixed-method study about career direction, declared and undeclared uncertainty (Orndorff & Herr, 1996, as cited in Goodson, 2018).

College graduating students expand their concern to the national economy, the livelihood of the country, and the people; stability and social harmony in terms of employment do not focus on development and progress (Chen & Zeng, 2021). There is always a moment of process in switching careers for college students who are graduating

when they face uncertainty (Li et al., 2012, as cited by Cheng & Zeng, 2021). Thus, this student who experiences career uncertainty turns their decision-making capability into career indecision (Elyadi, 2006, as cited by Botha & Mostert, 2013).

Career Uncertainty

Wu et al. (2020), in their research, the term 'uncertainty' is defined as the subjects have "insufficient information or understanding about a situation, or the potential options, or the likelihood that they will occur, or their results". In the context of uncertainty in careers or career uncertainty, it is defined as any element related to job prospects that causes uneasiness to people. It focuses on the individual's sentiments of helplessness in dealing with a problem, and their sense of efficacy in dealing with it (Tien, Lin & Chen, 2005). Moreover, career uncertainty has been defined from the previous research as the ability to cannot identify their concrete aspirations or incapability to decide their occupational choices (Kelly & Lee, 2002; Staff et al., 2010 as cited in Edwin, Pulse, Alhiyari, Salvatierra & Martin, 2022).

The presence of several options in college experience and the choices that were not considered before among college students, their experiences in uncertainty arise as their interest evolves and progresses, and depends on the opportunity outcome of their future profession (Kwok, 2018). Uncertainty in one's career presents itself through lost opportunities, which has an impact on networking and institutional threads. Career uncertainty seems to complicate personal and familial circumstances as well (Skakni, Masdonati & Maggiori, 2020). Career uncertainty influenced how they defined and pursued professional success (Trevor-Roberts, Parker & Sandberg, 2019).

Career uncertainty may have an episodic presence not only within but also across the entire profession. Gayatri, Widanputra, Suputra and Rasmini (2019) states that it resulted in the uncertain feeling of an individual regarding their future career, even though they had already decided their future. Uncertainty affects the ways of thinking that roughly the career path is beyond control (Trevor-Roberts, Parker and Sandberg, 2019). The lack of confidence as a factor in their transition period in employment after graduation may result in career uncertainty that may influence one's life negatively and may provide conflict in its career-selection process (Mattison, 2011; Mostert, 2013).

Gurchiek's study (2022) revealed that 34% of respondents between the ages of 18 and 24 did not believe about using their current skill sets in the workplace, 33% didn't believe about managing their career's next stages, and 55% were feeling nervous about making that move. Power, Hughes, Cotter & Cannon, (2020) state that the transition period is the most crucial time for college students as they change settings from education to corporate labor. In addition, other informants applied to ten companies but waited and were accepted after several months, which led to self-doubt about their qualifications and agony. Another fresh graduate chooses their first job that aligns with the field discipline of their courses, but they are also open and willing to work with companies that are unrelated and irrelevant to their expertise in the field. This is the situation: they are not picky about the offers of limited jobs as long as they get the job opportunity.

In the Philippines, a study conducted by Matisson (2011), 72% of Filipino college students appear uncertain when it comes to their future career. This bigger prevalence of career uncertainty among students needs to delve deeper into its implications. In literature, career uncertainty varies especially in the Philippine context. According to Pagdanganan (2022), when students in higher education approach the end of their college life, they may experience or feel confusion, uncertainty, and lack of motivation with regard to their careers, and as stated by Dr. Joan Rifarael, this is called “post-graduation blues”. Even people who have decided what they want to do in the future may be concerned about what might happen in their professional lives. There will always be something beyond their control. Factors such as internal pressure, hunting for preferred jobs, and the aspects of low-paying jobs are the main challenges considered among fresh graduates.

Guay, Senecal, Gauthier, and Fernet (2003), as cited by Abaya-Garcia (2015), try to understand the interactions between the intra-individual and interpersonal. Career indecision is defined as “an inability to make a decision about the vocation one wishes to pursue” (p. 165). Also, Garcia (2015), states that parents and peers as Filipinos can affect their career decision-making as they are more influential, resulting in a lower feeling of being efficacious and autonomous.

According to Schadl, Sheppard, & Chen (2018), research studies about career certainty, career indecision, and uncertain college students appear conflicting and confusing from time to time, thus, possessing a lack of uniformity or having an invariable or inconsistent face in the field of scientific studies. In addition to this, demonstrating comparison between career certainty and indecision associated with students is scarcely defined due to a variety of approaches used in identifying the contrast of the said topics. These further states that the utilization of instruments to measure career indecision and the populations being assessed—differing by academic year level or by college program—are components contributing to this reason. This specifically pertains to the complex nature of career uncertainty and its role as being in the field of research.

Research Questions

- 1. How do graduating college students' personal and environmental reasons shape their career uncertainty?*
- 2. How do graduating college students manage throughout their experience with career uncertainty?*
- 3. How do graduating college students make sense of their lived experiences of career uncertainty?*

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis was used by the researchers, a qualitative approach by Smith (2021), this will rely on methodical investigation of social processes in natural settings. It deals with people's experiences, how they behave, how they function, and how interactions shape relationships. The researchers' objective was to know the lived experiences of graduating college students experiencing career uncertainties. Exploring the factors lying beneath the experiences may help to understand how and what are the causes of the career uncertainty of the college graduating students.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the National Capital Region (NCR/Metro Manila). According to the Labor & Employment Department - NCR (DOLE-NCR) regional office, by 2022, the Philippines projects a thousand to join the employment's force of labor as the Philippine graduation season begins. In NCR alone, there are 434 higher education institutions with more than 2,000 course offerings which also contributes in the region being with the highest number of graduates (Department of Labor and Employment, 2022; Tutor et al., 2021).

Key Informant Selection

The researchers applied snowball technique as a sampling for non-probability strategy in which the research informants help recruit future volunteers for a study known as chain-referral sampling (Simkus, 2023). The researchers gathered 8 informants who are (1) graduating college students, (2) experiencing career uncertainty. In this study, it excludes those who are vulnerable in any condition in mental health and those who are working or employed.

Research Instruments

The researchers used a screening tool to assess the recommended informants in their level of career uncertainty through the use of Career Decision-making Difficulty Questionnaire (CDDQ) of Gati, Krausz, & Osipow (1996). An interview guide with 10 open-ended questions through a semi-structured interview type was used by the researchers. The initial three inquiries aim to obtain the demographic data profile of the respondents. Another question sets asks about the lived encounters during career uncertainty and how career uncertainty affects their decision-making. Experts from the psychological field reviewed and validated the instruments in research, preceding to the process of data collection. This allows the informants to provide answers independently through the semi-structured type, this explores the experiences and their own viewpoints as it allows the researchers to have some follow-up inquiries from the participants (Adams, 2015). Moreover, the study administered a mobile-based voice recording application to obtain necessary data during the interview session.

Data Collection

The Institutional Ethics Review Committee approvals begins the process of Data collection proper. Information forms for informants such as "Informed Consent" serve up as an arrangement if whether the subject wants to take part in the research, fully aware of its type and objectives (Manti & Licari, 2018). After acquiring the informed consent from informants, the researchers will start the semi-structured interview via one-on-one face-to-face interview. One meeting will be held with each informant to establish a relationship, gather information, and debrief. The session with the informants will last no more than an hour and a half. The researchers will record and transcribe the interviews for data analysis, while ensuring the informants s' privacy and confidentiality. Finally, the researchers will review the informants and proceed with data analysis.

Data Analysis

Once the data collection was done, researchers will apply an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis as prescribed by Willig & Wendy (2018). During the initial phase of reading, the researchers made observations upon reviewing the transcript material. Subsequently, our focus shift towards looking for themes and assigning them names to categorize them. The next stage involves connecting these themes to form a coherent analysis. Afterward, the researchers will move on to the next stage of the process, which involves continuing the analysis to other cases. Once the researchers have completed this step, the researchers can begin writing up the meanings that emerge from the participants' experiences. Finally, the researchers will have the conclusion by presenting an accessible introduction to IPA for the reader.

RESULTS

Informants

Informant A is a 21-year-old student taking a bachelor's degree in food and service management at a technical college located in the city of Marikina. She is currently on her fourth-year level in college and has a target graduation date in July, in the year 2024.

Informant B is a 21-year-old student taking a bachelor's degree in food and service management at a technical college located in the city of Marikina. He is currently on her fourth-year level in college and has a target graduation date in 2024.

Informant C is a 23-year-old student taking a Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) at a university located in the city of Makati. She is currently in her final year level of her 3-year course in college and expects to graduate in December, in the year 2024.

Informant D is a 21-year-old student taking a Bachelor's in Financial Management program at a university located in the city of Manila. He is currently on his fourth-year level in college and expects to graduate in 2024.

Informant E is a 21-year-old student taking a Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teachers Education (BTVTEd) with the major of Electronics Technology program at a technical college located in the city of Marikina. He is currently on her fourth-year level in college and has a target graduation date in August, year 2024.

Informant F is a 20-year-old student taking a Bachelor of Science in Public Health (BSPH) program at a university located in the city of Manila. She is currently in her fourth-year level in college and expects to graduate in 2024.

Informant G is a 21-year-old student taking a Bachelor of Science in Psychology (BS Psych) program at a university located in the city of Manila. She is currently in her fourth-year level in college and expects to graduate in 2024.

Informant H is a 21-year-old student taking a Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (BTLED) major in Information and Communication Technology program at a polytechnic university located in the city of Manila. He/she is currently on his/her fourth-year level in college and expects to graduate in 2024.

Emerging themes and categories

1. Reasons of Career Uncertainty

Individuals' intrapersonal and interpersonal (actions) are factors that may cause career uncertainty. These reasons are the starting point of career uncertainty itself, which progresses to their present experience.

1.1 Personal reasons

Informants shared intrapersonal reasons such as skills, capabilities, personal difficulties, loss of interests, beliefs, perspectives and impressions as sources of uncertainty about a career.

"...(lost of interest) Ta's parang, parang hinahanap mo na ng ano, parang kung tutuloy mo pa ba or hindi na 'yung parang... Parang nagdoubt ka na sa sarili mo, 'yung ganon, tapos parang ano siya– nag-aano na rin siya eh, basta para siyang doubt na talaga sa sarili natin na 'yung pa ba 'yung magiging ikaw or gusto mo pa ba 'yung gan'yang course na kinuha mo, nagkakaroon ka na ng self-doubt." (...(lost of interest), Then it's like, it got to a point wherein I'm having dialogues with myself if I should still pursue my passion. [cooking as a passion related to a college program]. It feels like you're doubting if the program I am pursuing still defines your personal interests or if I still really want to continue this program that I have enrolled myself in.) PA, L67-71

*"I don't know if it's neutral or... minsan kasi iniisip ko din na *long pause* if I would be successful, possible na maging successful ako someday...ehh... knowing na I have this *pause* skills na hindi naman parang enough *pause* sa...sa mga...*pause* trabaho na kinakailangan*

*nila... Yeah! I do feel uncertain rin, thinking about *pause* the future. Eh, ang pangit talaga ng technical skills ko, eh 'yung mga jobs ngayon (need high skill) so yea i do feel it at times... pero.. ayon mga ganon."* (I don't know if it's neutral but sometimes, I'm thinking if I would become successful. Although I may be successful someday knowing that I have these skills, it seems that it is not suitable for the job description that they are looking for. I do feel uncertain thinking about the future since I feel that my technical skills are not competent enough to qualify for jobs that are seeking for individuals with high skills.) PC, L34-36, 77-79

"So, parang ang ano, ang point ko lang is...uhm, yung naging factor sa...parang personal factor yun, uhhh... yung feeling of uncertainty ko ngayon is yung... ano, yung mga decision ko sa buhay. Minsan umo-oo ako, minsan hindi. Minsan, hinahayaan ko nalang, minsan hindi. Parang in my whole life, uncertain talaga ako. Uh, ayun nga, wala akong concrete na foundation on what I envision who I am, yung paglaki" (So, my point is that there is a personal factor that is affecting my feeling of uncertainty towards my decision making in life. There are no in-between with my answers. Sometimes, I say 'yes' or 'no', sometimes I just let things go with the flow. In my whole life, I have been uncertain and no concrete foundation on what I envision of who I am.) PE, L150-154, 156-157

1.2 Environmental reasons

Informants share interpersonal reasons outside of their control, such as unexpected changes or the need to change their career plans as a result of uncertainty about their career.

"...(family expectations) Ano... parang 'yung nagiging ano niya, contribute sa akin sa external factors, ano siya syempre ano nakaka-ano siya parang (pressure sa family)... tas 'yung mga syempre inaano ka nila na 'yung feeling na sinasabi nila na ga-graduate na ganon, trabaho." ((family expectations) The external factors that are contributing with my uncertainty is the pressure that my family is giving. Especially when they are saying that I would be graduating soon and should have decent work.) PA, L48-51

"...(natatakot na baka walang mangyari at ma-accomplish sa future) so... parang doon nanggagaling yung uncertainty ko sa career ko which is, paano kapag hindi nag work yung ganito, paano kung hindi nag work yung sa mga plano so, parang doon na ko nagkakaroon ng uncertainty. Kaya sa environment siguro, ayun din, kaya siguro nagiging uncertain ako kasi hindi din certain sila, parang kumbaga, hindi sila sure sa path nila, parang ganon din ako." (So this is where my uncertainty with my career is rooted. I was anxiously thinking about the 'what ifs' if things did not work according to plan. I think my environment is also a factor contributing to my uncertainty; when I feel like others are uncertain about their path.) PE, L82-85, 117-119

2. Challenges in experiencing career uncertainty

The existence of career uncertainty has a notable role in the graduating college students' experiences. With their final year in tertiary education, conflicts and struggles, aside from academics, extend to their personal uneasiness, especially with the forthcoming graduation.

2.1 Personal Challenges

Internal challenges continue to arise in the moment of the existence of career uncertainty. Graduating college students experience struggle with decision-making, anxiety, being indecisive, demotivation with feelings of being lost. These difficulties interfere in their daily lives and with the positive perception of themselves in the future.

"...out of nowhere, nagchat ako sa magulang ko na gusto ko talagang umuwi ng (home place) kasi parang 'di ko na talaga kaya." (...out of nowhere, I started a conversation (using the Messenger app) with my parents expressing myself in a demotivated tone saying that I really want to go home, because I feel like I cannot do it anymore.) PD, L131-133

"...nahihirapan akong mag-look into the future, sobra...like hindi ko makita saan ako 10 years from now." (...I am having a difficulty to look into the future, I cannot see myself 10 years from now.) PF, L46-47

3. Manifestation of Career Uncertainty

The manifestation of career uncertainty surfaces in the senior year of graduating college students upon their internal and external activities. It has salient effects in all physical, emotional, and cognitive aspects that results in uneasiness within themselves.

3.1 Physical Manifestations

Physical wellness is one of the essential components for graduating college students as they work diligently to prepare for the forthcoming graduation. Due to uncertainty, troubles with their physical health such as stress, unhealthy eating habits, and difficulty sleeping began to interfere with their physiological well-being and daily routine.

"...minsan sa sobrang stress 'di na ko nakakatulog talaga. Ahm... ayun, napapakain talaga ako ng mga 2am, 3am, mga ganung oras." (Sometimes, due to stress, I'm having a hard time falling asleep and because of that, I find myself binge eating at around 2 to 3 in the morning.) PD, L94-95

"...nakakapagod kasi parang...nakaka drain siya ng energy, physically, mentally..." (...It's tiring because it's draining my energy – physically and mentally...) PE, L56-57

3.2 Emotional Manifestation

With the presence of career uncertainty, graduating college students have also encountered disadvantages in their emotional well-being and may affect their ability to keep up with their day-to-day academic activities in higher education. It may affect the way they perceive or grasp their plans, decisions, and further actions in preparation for their future, especially when the expected graduation is approaching.

3.2.1 Demotivation

This involves losing passion in spite of re-seeking the desire to continue and having unclear vision of their future career. Informants A and D experience the emotional manifestation of career uncertainty that results in demotivation. This lack of motivation interferes with the stability of their emotions, as well as their capacity to initiate doing and achieving particular activities.

“...parang umabot yata na parang nawala na talaga ‘yung passion ko sa ganun, nafi-feel ko na sobrang uncertain na ako parang hinahanap ko kasi ulit ‘yung desire.” (...It’s feels like I have gotten to a point where my passion is gone and so I feel uncertain and I am trying to look for that “desire” again.) PA, L66-84

“Parang wala din talaga ‘kong makitang ah career path noon pa...” (I feel like I cannot see myself in any career path even before...) PD, L17-18

3.2.2 Pressure (as influence)

Another emotional manifestation of career uncertainty results in pressure as Informant A and F experienced. This involves internal pressure from your family, friends, and the society which has a bigger role of eliciting expectations. Pressure interferes with the way they construct goals and plans for the future due to responsibility and moments of questioning their own abilities regarding their ambitions.

“...nakaka-pressure kasi siya kasi syempre ‘pag graduating tas ‘yung mga family mo pa... Parang inaano nila na mag-aano ka na, ‘yung kailangan may trabaho ka na, ano parang ikaw na ‘yung bubuhay sa amin ganon. ‘Yun ‘yung mas nakaka-cause talaga sa’kin now kahit ako sa sarili ko nape-pressure na rin.” (...I feel pressured because of course I’m a graduating student and my family on the other hand is putting pressure on things such as: “I must find a job because I am the main provider in sustaining our living expenses.” It caused me to feel pressured.) PA, L49-53

“Ta’s siguro meron na din sa point na – kasi bunso ako sa amin, so nauna ko nang nakita ‘yong ano... ‘yong kuya ko– yong mga kuya ko, kumbaga diba ‘ay successful na sila’ dito ganyan, ganyan. So, medyo nakaka pressure ganon.” (At one point, as the youngest in the family, I already witnessed how successful my older brother have been in different aspects in life. So, there is a growing pressure on my behalf.) PF, L58-60

3.2.3 Anxiousness

Career uncertainty manifests emotionally through anxiousness from social expectations from people whom they have intimate relationships with, such as members of the family and/or their significant others, that are settled with their careers. Anxiousness is a heightened worry that affects their discernment of their future. As expressed by Informants D and H, they lack a sense of direction on how they would build their own future.

“Ayaw ko naman mag mukhang palamunin... makatulong sa pamilya and para sa future family ko rin if ever man... pinaka worry ko talaga diyan is, actually dahil may jowa nga talaga ako iniisip ko din iniisip ko din talaga ‘yung parang magiging future ko narin with her.” (I don’t want to look as if I’m a burden and loafing around in our family... so I may be able to help them and my future family, if ever... I worry a lot since I have a partner and I also consider my future with her.) PD, L98-99

“...dito po sa bahay usually mga kasama ko po dito is professional na so parang ano pagnakikita mo silang may ginagawa ano certain na sila sa career nila... So ayun nakaka anxious pag parang ikaw di ka sure kung parang anong gusto mong gawin. So parang ayun nagkaka anxious ako na pano nila ginawa yon or pano sila nagcome up na ayun na yung gagawin nila for the rest of their life ganun.” (...I live together with my older siblings who have been successful in their careers. And whenever I see them starting a certain project towards their career enhancement, I feel anxious as if I am not sure on what things I really want to do. That is why I really feel anxious on how they are able to do these things effortlessly for the rest of their lives.) PH, L49-53

3.2.4 Excitement

On the other hand, career uncertainty also results in excitement which Informants A and E experienced. However, the excitement they expressed is associated with a combination of the feeling of pressure and fear. This involves excitement to the expected graduation event, including the idea of what career they would have in the future. Moreover, this excitement also produced worry about their future, such as the thought of failing.

“...‘pag sinabing graduation parang nakaka-excite siya at the same time nakaka-pressure...” (...When they are talking about graduation, I feel excited but at the same time, I am also pressured...) PA, L22-23

“...parang somewhere in the middle siguro, hindi lang ako—hindi ako excited, hindi rin ako natatakot, parang ganon. Natatakot lang ako siguro na may—‘yung takot nalang siguro na baka hindi ko ma-accomplish or sa pinili ko, walang mangyari...” (...Maybe somewhere in the middle, I feel like I am not the only one who is experiencing thoughts such as “I am not excited

nor afraid” but at the same time, there is a part of me that is afraid out of fear that I won’t be able to accomplish something...) PE, L80-82

3.3 Cognitive Manifestation

In the face of career uncertainty, graduating college students’ cognitive state is affected by considering many options and making judgments in relation to their chosen program in tertiary education and their future careers. This mainly entails an evaluation of their preferences, life decisions, and possibilities.

3.3.1 Confusion

In some instances when they are in the state of experiencing career uncertainty, it gives rise to confusion or a state of being confused as Informants B & G experienced. This includes a manner of assessing oneself with its limitations and capabilities, and in addition to this, the manner of choosing over an option versus another option related to their academics.

“Pero ang problema, habang tumatagal eh makakayanan ko ba?”
(My dilemma as time goes by lies in whether will I be able to continue and carry on?) PB, L73

“...mag—tutuloy ko ba ‘yung psych or ‘yung Masscom?” (Should I just pursue Psychology or try my possibilities in Mass Communication Program?) PG, L86-87

3.3.2 Doubt

Another cognitive manifestation of career uncertainty also results in doubt as Informants G & H expressed. Similar to confusion, an evaluation regarding one’s competence also occurs in this part. It contrasts primarily with the manner of choosing an option versus another option but with the consideration of the possible consequences or results that may transpire in the future when they would make a decision.

“...what if na-try ko na yung dalawang setting, o tatlong setting, tas in the future hindi naman pala...” (...What if I allowed myself to try two to three different settings only to find out in the future that it was not meant for me?...) PG, L68-69

“...parang lagi parang andon yung thought na mali yung course na pinasukan mo in the first place....” (...There’s always a thought that the program which I’ve entered in the first place is a mistake...) PH, L39-41

3.3.3 Regret

Informants B & H reported dealing with regret as they experience career uncertainty. This pertains to their interfering realization with the current college programs they are taking, wherein they facilitate insights about the relevance and benefits that their college courses will contribute to their future careers. Moreover, this influences them to

manifest a sense of longing and a thought of missing an opportunity to reconsider alternative approaches in choosing an ideal course in college.

“Pero may time din na dapat di ko ‘to pinili kasi medyo hindi ko rin naman gusto rin ‘to.” (But sometimes, I thought that maybe I should have not chosen this program because there is a small part of me that doesn't like this as well.) PB, L36-37

“...lagi kong iniisip na siguro dapat hindi nalang ako nagsettle dito sa program na ‘to...” (...I always think that I should have not settled in this program...) PH, L40-41

4. Managing the Career Uncertainty: Coping Efficacy

As they continue to acknowledge the presence of career uncertainty, the graduating college students were able to become aware of how these challenges affect them. Their established social connections assume the role of the principal coping efficacy in managing this experience by providing social support.

4.1 Social Support

In the face of career uncertainty, graduating college students adapt themselves through the experience from the support provided by their social bonds. This involves their family, peers, the academe, and organization that are alongside them from the past until up to the present.

4.1.1 Family

Informants share their coping experiences in managing career uncertainty through their family as a basic, yet essential part of society that can easily turn to comfort, understanding, and support them.

“...sa parents ko, they ano sinabi nila na kahit tapusin ko muna yung course ko ngayon tas mag-aral, magtake nalang daw ulit ako after graduating” (...My parents compromised with me to finish the program where I am currently enrolled and right after I graduate will I be able to study any program that I want.) PD, L184-185

“...yung support ng family, ganyan. Uh, kung ano yung gusto, okay lang sa kanila, ganyan. Isa yun sa resources.” (...One of my resources is my family who supports my decisions on what I want to pursue.) PG, L107-108

4.1.2 Peers

The maintaining social relationships the informants have, has provided a sense of support in managing their career uncertainty. This allowed them to seek guidance and during the difficult moments as well as the re-evaluation of their actions and decisions.

“...ayon shinishare ko nalang sa friends ko, madali lang sila mareach lalo na video call, messenger, ganyan. Isang chat lang, one call away naman sila...” (...I just share it to my friends because they are easy to reach out, especially on social media, like video call and Messenger, and the likes...) PF, 128-129

“...tinatry ko pong kausapin sila (friends) like pano kung ano yung gagawin natin pagkatapos” (...I am trying to talk and plan with my friends on what should we do next after we graduate.) PH, L34

4.1.3 Academe/Organization

Informants share their coping experiences in managing career uncertainty through the academe as their second home or the organization that is always with them.

“...nung nag face-to-face, bumalik yung dati kong ano learning ko. Then, ayun parang nasisimulan ko nang mahal in yung course ko.” (When face-to-face classes return, my desire of learning came back. Then is when I started to love my program.) PD, L69-71

“...yung mga blockmates ko po sobrang laking factor po kung pano ako nakapagcope since most po ng blockmates ko parang napunta po sila BTLED ICT ng hindi po nila gusto.” (...My blockmates play a huge factor in how I cope since most of them pursued BTLED ICT even if they didn't want to pursue it.) PH, L72-74

5. Persevering amidst career uncertainty

Graduating college students exhibit perseverance that emerges from themselves and their interpersonal relationships which generates a positive attitude. Throughout the negative experience of career uncertainty, they continue to adhere to their daily routines as a student and shows commitment to their chosen program.

5.1 Intrapersonal

The informant emphasizes that regardless of the uncertainty, they continue to risk, to seek, and to develop their passion within themselves such as engaging in old and new activities.

“...gusto kong i-bring back ulit ‘yung ganung feel, kaya parang ano, uhmm tina-try ko ulit magluto like, try new things...” (...I want to bring back that feeling again, that's why I'm trying to discover new hobbies such as cooking and trying new things.) PA, L86-87

5.2 Interpersonal

In the face of the demotivation brought by career uncertainty, the informant shares their experience of being driven in attempting to re-establish their motivation through the people that surround them.

“...‘yung mga ano syempre may mga kapatid ako like don, parang nagkakaroon ulit ako ng motivation, tapos ‘yung mga friends ko rin ‘pag nagshe-share ng mga problems like mino-motivate din nila ako...” (...of course, I have siblings and friends whom I can share my problems while they try to motivate me.) PA, L94-96

6. Making Sense with Career Uncertainty

Graduating college students' experiences with career uncertainty may have shown negatively through the challenges it caused especially in their senior year. These struggles however, shaped their own perception of the experience in which they are able to construct new meanings alongside with how they see themselves, the people around them, and the world they live in.

6.1 Uncertainty as an element of Personal Growth (Being a better person)

Graduating college students construe their experience with career uncertainty as a component for personal development. Continuing to view uncertainty as part of life, it has an inevitable impact on their day-to-day life.

“...based on my experience no, pwede ko siyang i-share sa iba na, some ano, pwede ko i-share sa iba na, I, too, feel that something ganyan, not to invalidate your feelings or that pero nakiki sympathize na din.” (Based on my experience, I can share some of my career uncertainties freely with anyone that I know without my feelings getting invalidated or knowing that they are sympathizing with me.) PE, L269-271

“...for me, deal with it in a short-term. Yung short-term dealings na yun, pwede mo siya magawa though ‘doing’ diba, kung hindi mo alam, kung uncertain ka, gawin mo lang. Pag nagkamali ka, that’s good, kasi ibig-sabihin, may matututunan ka. Kapag naging tama ka naman then that’s good, that works for you.” (...based on my experience, I can share it with others in a sympathizing manner that I also feel experience these short-term dealings in life such as career uncertainties by trying to avoid invalidating their feelings. These short-term dealings are possible through ‘doing’, right? If you don’t know, if you’re uncertain, just do it. If you make a mistake, that’s good; it only means that you’ll learn something. And if you’re right, then that’s good, that works for you.) PE, L278-281

6.2 Uncertainty as a Bridge for Social Connection

Uncertainty aids the gap connection of the graduating college students to their environment. Informants share their experience as they view the uncertainty bridging to reconnect with other people.

“...kasi nakita ko lang sa kanyang post tas kinausap ko sya randomly na “uy ikaw din pala”, natulungan namin ang isa’t-isa na para mamotivate namin sarili namin na “uy, hindi ka na mag-isa, nandito lang kami...” (I randomly saw his post online and decided to approach him by

acknowledging his post by saying “I noticed you are also experiencing the same thing”, we helped each other to motivate one another by acknowledging “You are not alone, we are here for you.”) PD, L199-202

“...always talk to your friends and family kasi nakakatulong din sila sa paghelp mo sa pagdecide...” (Always talk to your friends and family because they can also help in terms of decision making...) PG, L151-152

6.3 Uncertainty as a Steppingstone for Future Career

Making changes doesn't scare them, it helps them to explore new things. Informants share their view in uncertainty as one of the stepping stones for the future, for their career that helps them to be on the right path; to be on the right side without hesitation, without fear and with full motivation.

“So baka in the future, kapag nandon na ako sa point na yon na gusto ko baka sabihin nya na lang sa akin na ‘Thank you dahil triny mong hanapin talaga kung ano yong para sa’yo. Triny mong hindi lang yong want mo ‘yong kinokonsider mo kundi pano sya makakatulong sayo in the future’.” (So maybe in the future, if I get to that point which I really wanted, I would probably thank myself by saying ‘Thank you because you tried to find what is really meant for you. You tried not only because of what you want, but you considered as well on how it could help you in the future.) IF, L176-179

“...wag kayong masyadong mag dwell sa future kasi kung para saan talaga kayo, doon talaga kayo mapupunta... hindi lang ako yung uncertain sa career path, so titignan ko lang siya as normal... Part siya ng journey ng life.” (...Do not dwell too much on the future because there is the right place for you and you'll get there.. I am not the only one who is uncertain with my career path, so I'll look at it as a part of normal, a part of our journey in life.) PG, L148-149

Emergent Framework

The results of this study emerged to form a framework on the next page interprets the experience of Filipino graduating college students with career uncertainty. It emphasizes that career uncertainty branches out to the six emerging themes of this study, which includes the reasons of career uncertainty, the challenges and manifestations they deal with, and how they manage, persevere, and eventually grasp newfound meanings of the uncertainty. Individuals entail various reasons that dwell within the personal and environmental factors that result in the challenging experiences. This enables the career uncertainty to acquire manifestations physically, emotionally, and cognitively. Because of its challenges and manifestation, the Informants came with managing their lived experiences through perseverance. Moreover, the Informants expressed the idea that career uncertainty is not negative at all, thus, they continue to make sense of it and live with it as a sign of resilience and purpose.

Figure 2. Graduating college students' lived experiences model of career uncertainty

DISCUSSION

The graduating college students acknowledge that career uncertainty has been impactful on their future career. They are expected to graduate as Batch 2024 as the conclusion of the academic year, but they can't specify what their job will be after graduation, this is the previous definition of the career uncertainty according to Kelly & Lee, (2002); Staff et al., (2010) as cited in Edwin et al., (2022). The feeling of uncertainty starts to surface during decision-making when entering a chosen baccalaureate program. Uncertainty in the career originates from their chosen program before entering college has a lack of opportunities, some of the program they've chosen has too many opportunities to choose, and the indecisiveness or due to their personality. This shows that career uncertainty surfaces by the time that they step-foot with their chosen course and enter higher education as stated by Goodson (2018).

Also, this study finds that as the forthcoming graduation of the college students, education to labor transition was a delicate time as stated by Power, et al. (2020). The manifestation of career uncertainty results in emotional manifestation such as confusion and demotivation which was supported by Pagdanganan (2022). Additionally, uncertain graduating college students are more concerned about their futures because of many factors that they can encounter along the way. Ebner et al., 2021 cited that one of them is the inability to find an appropriate job that is aligned to their skills. Most of them believe that they are not competent enough and their present skills cannot be used in their future workplace as stated by Gurchiek (2022). This is one of the main factors considered by Mattison (2010); Mostert (2013), the lack of confidence that can affect the career-selection and may view life negatively because of its influence.

Unveiling the starting point of career uncertainty helps us delve into the understanding of the experiences of the informants. In this study, before the actual experience of career uncertainty, underlying factors from their personal and environmental experience initiates the feeling of uncertainty. Reasons affect the ways of thinking that roughly the career path is beyond control Trevor-Roberts, Parker and Sandberg, (2019) that may change their interests, performance and beliefs. As something is beyond control as evident from Kwok (2018) that several options in college experience and the choices that were not considered before among college students, their experiences in uncertainty arise as their interest evolves and progresses, and depends on the outcome of their future profession. Their personal and environmental reasons resulting in the emerging of the categories of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive experience which are also evident on the career uncertainty model of Tien, Lin, & Chen (2005).

Despite its negative effects, the informants continue to view career uncertainty with positivity. The *bahala na* (determinism) and *kapwa* (shared identity) of Sikolohiyang Pilipino emerge as they continue to live with uncertainty, they continue to explore new things in their life. The behavior of *bahala na* of the informants shows Lagmay's (1977) interpretation of *bahala na* as of convincing themselves that they are prepared to tackle the difficult path or situation before them and will do everything to achieve their goals (Pe-

Pua & Protacio-Marcelino, 2000). It is a challenge for graduating college students to have a drive in the middle of uncertainty, yet they still continue to strive through the aspect of *kapwa*. It is a feeling that there are other people that can lean from the difficult situation and help them to cope with the feeling of uncertainty. Enriquez (1994) as cited by Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino (2000) defined the *kapwa* as “*the heart of the structure of Filipino values*” and considered it as “*the core of Filipino Social Psychology.*” The *bahala na* of Lagmay and *kapwa* of Enriquez both mirror the intrapersonal and interpersonal drive of the informants. Moreover, when dealing with career uncertainty, it highlights the crucial role of social support from family, friends, and the academic community. As reflected in the findings, people carry on along with their interpersonal relationships demonstrating that career uncertainty is intertwined with social connections.

Gayatri, et al., (2019) cites that there is always something ‘out of control’ in the presence of uncertainty among individuals’ career path, however, people still decide what to do even with an uncertain future. The graduating college students in this study expressed that they view their career uncertainty as an advantageous encounter, an opportunity to continue to explore accompanied with hope, and as a steppingstone on how they will perceive their future career. This also aligns with the characteristic of Filipino resilience among college students wherein Nicomedes, Gamad, & Dinglasa (2020), asserted that they remain consistent or stable on striving despite the existence of hardships, difficulties, and misfortune. In addition to this, the aforementioned study further states that being open to perceived problems and having supportive social groups also contribute with the formation of resilience, therefore, the emerging demeanor of optimism.

While the COVID-19 pandemic impacts lives resulting in economic recessions and the lack of social connectedness (Cleofas, 2020), graduating college students in this study continue in making sense with uncertainty as a bridge of social connection. This also highlights the *pakikipagkapwa* of Enriquez (1994) cited by Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino (2000), as they continue to help other people as a fellow and not only as a companion. That even though they are accompanied by the feeling of uneasiness regarding their future careers, graduating college students view their experience as cumulative through the lens of *pakikipagkapwa*, wherein a connection and identity is shared.

Conclusions

This study aimed to know the lived experiences of graduating college students who are experiencing career uncertainty and determine the causes lying beneath the said phenomenon for the purpose of fostering recognition, understanding, and foundation to commence a further-developed and more competent systematic career counseling and interventions among academic institutions, as well as school counselors, to accommodate students in tertiary education who are experiencing uncertainty towards their future careers.

Career uncertainty has become a phenomenon among graduating college students due to a necessary consideration for having a career path as their graduation is

set to take place. By the utilization of semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions, this study was able to obtain information regarding the informants' remarks about career uncertainty based on their subjective experiences and perspectives. It expressed that graduating college students' career uncertainty is a perceived worry about their future walk of life associated with different attributes such as lack of direction, indecisiveness, and academic course-related challenges. It was evident that personal challenges mainly manifested through their career uncertainty physically, emotionally, and cognitively. Moreover, in connection with managing their career uncertainty, it is found that social support plays a substantial role as they face these challenges, this mainly involves family, peers, and the academic community. This extends to their insight regarding their lived experiences about career uncertainty, which shows indication of openness, perseverance, and an optimistic behavior despite the occurrence of adversity and the negative effects that surfaced. They view these challenges as a valuable part of their journey in their life. Some concepts of Sikolohiyang Pilipino were also mentioned in this study to further explain how the unique experiences of the graduating college students lived in the moment of uncertainty can be understood in the Philippine context. This entails how 21st century Filipino young adults who are considered in the last year of their academic year are resilient to the feeling of uncertainty.

Recommendations

This study was able to provide conceptualized knowledge of the aspects of career uncertainty from the lived experiences of graduating college students in the Philippines which yields limited exploration. Moreover, realizations for recommendations are produced for future researchers to bridge more gaps in the literature regarding Career Uncertainty in the Philippines. First, since this study was only limited to the graduating college students in the National Capital Region in the Philippines, the researchers recommend expanding the locale and the key informants of the study. Also, to further extend the understanding of the phenomenon, choosing different levels of students or a specific baccalaureate program to identify the differences of their uncertainty. In line with this, various approaches are encouraged to be utilized to enrich and deepen the concept of Career Uncertainty. It is highly recommended to apply a grounded theory approach as the results exhibit a process from which the phenomenon of career uncertainty started to its current experience. Some of the data shows that emerging themes always lead to progression and show a glimpse of the process of their experiences with career uncertainty. This may also help us understand how the career uncertainty process is experienced in the Philippine context and the differences between the 2005 theory of Tien, Lin, and Chen from Taiwan. Second, a quantitative approach may be applied to identify the levels of uncertainty of the informants and to enhance the generalization capacity of the study. In view of the arising concerns with the experience of career uncertainty, the development of an enhanced and comprehensive systematic career counseling and interventions can aid the students dealing with the uncertainty after college entrance examinations and/or before entering their chosen baccalaureate program in higher educational institutions. Center for guidance services and central placement offices can also partner through the local government and non-government organizations to also help expand this research and bring it to the communities. Lastly,

the international community can also link to explore and adapt their interventions and affiliate along with universities and colleges in the Philippines to further delve into different interpretations for a diverse, cultural variations of the phenomenon.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to the 2017 APA Ethical Standards and used several of the ethical principles in conducting the study to ensure that this study prioritized everyone's safety which includes (1) approval from the institution, (2) informed consent form, (3) privacy and confidentiality, (4) anonymity of the informants, and (5) beneficence and nonmaleficence. As the researchers are not yet professionals, in the event that any of the informants experienced a negative emotional reaction or psychological stress, a guidance counselor was available to help them process their emotions. The Institutional Ethics Review Committee's approval was obtained conducting the research protocol. The researchers also understand that the informants may decide to revoke or withdraw at any time and the researchers have also the right to suspend the interview if they do so. The researchers strictly followed the ethical standards to prevent harm and effects to our informants.

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